

DERIVATIVES OF 3-(*p*-METHOXYPHENYL)-CYCLOHEXANONE

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A method of preparation of 3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone from 5-*p*-methoxyphenyldihydroresorcinol is recorded. Banerjee's claim to the synthesis of the above ketone could not be confirmed. The ketone, prepared by him, is shown to be 3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)- Δ^2 -cyclohexanone, synthesised from *o*-chloro-*p*-methoxypropiphenone and ethyl sodioacetoacetate.

In connection with certain investigations which are in progress in these laboratories it seemed desirable to obtain a supply of 3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone (I). The present communication deals with a number of experiments which led to the development of a satisfactory preparative method for this ketone which does not appear to have been made hitherto.

A perusal of the work of Crossley and his co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 63; 1911, 99, 1101; also Byod, Clifford, Probert, *ibid.*, 1920, 117, 1388) on the synthesis of substituted cyclohexanones suggested that 5-*p*-methoxyphenyldihydroresorcinol (II) might prove to be a valuable intermediate for the preparation of the ketone (I), more particularly since, the substituted dihydroresorcinol (II) can now be prepared in any desired quantity (Vorländer, *Annalen*, 1897, 294, 310; Hinkel, Ayling and Dippy, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 540) by the condensation of anisalacetone with ethyl sodiomalonate (Vorländer's reaction) followed by hydrolysis of the resulting product and subsequent removal of carbon dioxide (Friedmann, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1936, ii, 146, 65).

On treatment with phosphorus trichloride in presence of dry chloroform 5-*p*-methoxyphenyldihydroresorcinol (II) behaves in the expected manner (*cf.* Crossley and Le Sueur, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 494; 1905, 87, 1488), and yields 5-chloro-3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)- Δ^5 -cyclohexanone (III), m.p. 70°. The latter on reduction with sodium and moist ether

gives 3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanol (IV), m.p. 83-84° in a moderate yield. This on oxidation with Beckmann's chromic acid mixture, in the usual way, affords the desired ketone (I), b.p. 153-54°/4 mm. (*semicarbazone*, m.p. 193-94°).

Owing to the many steps involved the overall yield of the ketone (I) obtained in the above series of reactions is not, however, so good as could be desired. This difficulty is finally overcome by directly hydrogenating the chloroketone (III) in presence of colloidal palladium (Skita and Franck, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 2862; France, Heilbron and Hey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 1219) which proves to be most suitable for the preparation of the ketone (I) in appreciable quantities.

The properties of the ketone, thus obtained, are, however, quite different from those attributed to 3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone prepared by Banerjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 576) by another route.

In view of this it seemed desirable to re-examine the work of Banerjee (*loc. cit.*). Banerjee prepared his ketone through the following series of reactions: Ethyl γ -anisoylbutyrate on treatment with ethyl bromoacetate and zinc yielded the unstable δ -lactonic ester (V), which was reduced with zinc dust and caustic soda to give a crystalline acid, m.p. $154-55^\circ$, which Banerjee regarded as β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-pimelic acid (VI). The latter on ketonisation under the customary experimental conditions (Dieckmann's reaction) furnished 3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone (I).

It is now found, however, that the δ -lactonic ester (V) on boiling with alcoholic potash *alone* undergoes hydrolysis with the formation of the crystalline acid, m.p. $153-54^\circ$ described by Banerjee (*loc. cit.*). Clearly, the acid is unsaturated, since it rapidly decolourises bromine and permanganate, a fact apparently overlooked by Banerjee.

Obviously, the unsaturated acid, m.p. $154-55^\circ$ can have either of the formulae (VII) or (VIII).

The corresponding diethyl ester, moreover, readily absorbs *one* equivalent of hydrogen in presence of Adam's platinum oxide catalyst at the ordinary temperature with the formation of a saturated ester (as VI) which on hydrolysis, affords β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-pimelic acid (VI), m.p. $82-83^\circ$. The latter on ketonisation with acetic anhydride (Blanc's reaction) smoothly furnishes 3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone (I), identical in every way with the product described above.

The unsaturated acid (VII) or (VIII), m.p. $154-55^\circ$, on the other hand, under similar conditions furnishes a solid ketone, m.p. 84° , (*semicarbazone*, m.p. $218-19^\circ$), evidently, identical with Banerjee's ketone (*loc. cit.*). It would appear from the foregoing observations, that the solid ketone, first prepared by Banerjee, must be correctly represented as 3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)- Δ^2 -cyclohexenone (IX). This also follows, because, the latter on hydrogenation over

Adam's catalyst is quantitatively converted into 3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone (I).

In order to obtain further evidence on this point, the unsaturated ketone (IX) has been synthesised by the action of ω -chloro-*p*-methoxypropiofenone (Kenner and Statham, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 301) on ethyl sodio-acetoacetate followed by simultaneous hydrolysis and ring-closure of the resulting product by means of dilute sodium hydroxide.

The foregoing synthesis which leaves no room for doubt regarding the structure of the unsaturated ketone is precisely analogous to the formation of 3-phenyl- Δ^2 -cyclopentenone from ethyl phenacylacetate (Borsche, *Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 194).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

5-*p*-Methoxyphenyldihydroresorcinol (II) required was prepared by the condensation of anisalacetone ("Organic Synthesis" Vol. I, p. 71) with ethyl sodiomalonate in the usual way. The condensation product is best hydrolysed according to the method of Friedmann (*loc. cit.*). It has m.p. 184° after one crystallisation from dilute acetic acid. Hiinkel, Åyling, and Dippy (*loc. cit.*) give m.p. 175° (decomp.).

5-Chloro-3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)- Δ^5 -cyclohexenone (III).—A mixture of 5-*p*-methoxyphenyldihydroresorcinol (65.4 g.), dry chloroform (160 c.c.) and phosphorus trichloride (15 c.c.) was heated under reflux on the water-bath for 4 hours. The excess of chloroform was distilled off on the water-bath, the residue was mixed with ice-water and repeatedly extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed successively with a 4% solution of sodium hydroxide and water, dried, and evaporated. The residual brown oil was carefully distilled under reduced pressure when almost the whole quantity boiled at 210°/11 mm. and solidified to a crystalline mass. On recrystallisation from light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) it formed beautiful, colourless needles, m.p. 70°, yield, 34.4 g. (Found: Cl, 14.9. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 15.01 per cent).

3-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanol (IV).—Sodium (9 g.), cut into thin slices, was gradually introduced to a solution of the foregoing chloroketone (6.4 g.) in ether (100 c.c.) kept over water (100 c.c.) contained in a flask provided with a reflux condenser through which ice-cold water was allowed to circulate. When no more unreacted sodium remained the ethereal solution was separated, washed with water, dried over potassium carbonate and distilled. 3-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanol distilled at 165°/5 mm. as a colourless liquid which quickly solidified to a crystalline mass. On purification from light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) it formed transparent needles, m.p. 83-84°. (Found: C, 75.21; H, 8.73. $C_{13}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 75.71; H, 8.74 per cent).

3-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone (I). (1) From 3-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanol (IV).—The alcohol (14 g.) was well shaken with an excess of Beckmann's chromic acid mixture (126 g.), the mixture became warm and in a few minutes the oxidation was complete. The whole was finally warmed to 50°-60° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, cooled, diluted with water and repeatedly extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water, dried and evaporated. The residual oil was purified by distillation under reduced pressure. 3-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone formed a colourless, refracting liquid, b.p. 155°/4 mm.

(2) From 5-Chloro-3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)- Δ^5 -cyclohexanone (III).—The chloroketone (34.4 g.) dissolved in absolute alcohol (150 c.c.) was shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen with the addition of gum arabic (0.3 g.), dissolved in a little water, and palladium chloride (0.3 g.) until one equivalent of hydrogen was taken up. The catalyst was filtered off, and the excess of solvent evaporated. The residual oil on distillation under reduced pressure gave 3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone (25 g.) as a colourless liquid, b.p. 153-54°/4 mm. (Found: C, 76.0; H, 7.9. $C_{13}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 76.47; H, 7.86 per cent). The semicarbazone crystallises from rectified spirit in clusters of glistening prisms, m.p. 193-94°. (Found: C, 63.8; H, 7.2. $C_{11}H_{10}O_2N_2$ requires C, 64.2; H, 7.2 per cent).

Condensation of Ethyl γ -Anisoylbutyrate with Ethyl Bromoacetate: Formation of the Unsaturated Acid (VII or VIII).—Ethyl γ -anisoylbutyrate (14 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (10 c.c.), zinc wool (7.5 g.), and benzene (45 c.c.) were heated under reflux with the addition of a crystal of iodine as described by Banerjee (*loc. cit.*). The product was decomposed

with ice and an excess of dilute sulphuric acid, the benzene layer was isolated, washed with water, and then repeatedly extracted with a 10 % solution of caustic soda until a test portion no longer gave any turbidity on acidification. The alkaline solution was acidified and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed, dried and distilled. The residual viscous oil (12 g.) was hydrolysed by boiling with an excess of 10 % alcoholic potash (3 mols.). The excess of alcohol was removed from the water-bath as completely as possible. The alkaline solution was extracted with ether in order to remove neutral impurities, separated, and cautiously acidified with hydrochloric acid. The solution was then extracted several times with ether, the ethereal solution washed, dried, and evaporated. The residue (10 g.) solidified on scratching. The benzene solution on evaporation yielded a small residue (5g.) which eventually solidified and proved to be the unchanged keto-ester. The crude acid (10 g.) obtained was esterified with alcohol (75 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (5 c.c.) in the usual way. The ethyl ester formed a colourless liquid, b. p. 189-92°/4mm., yield 6.7 g. It rapidly decolourises a solution of bromine in carbon disulphide.

Hydrolysis with Alcoholic Potash.—The ester (1 g.) was refluxed with an excess of 10 per cent alcoholic potash (3 mols.), the excess of alcohol was removed on the water-bath. The alkaline solution was extracted with ether, acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and repeatedly extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water, dried and evaporated. The residue on keeping in an evacuated desiccator solidified to a crystalline mass and on purification from aqueous alcohol (charcoal) formed colourless crystals, m. p. 154-55°. A solution of the unsaturated acid in sodium carbonate rapidly decolourises potassium permanganate solution. (Found: C, 63.5; H, 6.3. $C_{14}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 63.63; H, 6.1 per cent).

*β -(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-pimelic Acid. (VI)*—The foregoing unsaturated ester (4.7 g.) dissolved in absolute alcohol (20 c.c.) was shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen with Adam's platinum oxide catalyst (0.05 g.) until the calculated quantity of hydrogen (375 c.c.) was absorbed. The solution was filtered from the platinum which was also washed once with alcohol. The excess of alcohol was removed and the residual oil on distillation yielded ethyl β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-pimelate (4.5 g.) boiling at 199°/5mm. (Found: C, 66.6; H, 8.1. $C_{18}H_{26}O_5$ requires C, 67.1; H, 8.1 per cent). The ester on hydrolysis with an excess of 10 % alcoholic potash in the usual way gave the acid as a crystalline solid which on recrystallisation from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (b. p. 80°-100°) formed minute prisms, m. p. 92-93°. (Found: C, 63.3; H, 6.9. $C_{14}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 63.16; H, 6.7 per cent).

Ketonisation.—The acid (5 g.) was heated with an excess of acetic anhydride under reflux on the sand-bath for 5 hours. The excess of acetic acid and acetic anhydride was then removed at the water pump and the residue distilled in an oil-pump. The ketone had b. p. 156-58°/5mm. yield 65 per cent. It was characterised as 3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone by its b. p. and by the preparation of the semicarbazone, m. p. 193-94°.

The unsaturated acid, m. p. 154-55°, on ketonisation yielded a crystalline unsaturated ketone, m. p. 84°, (semicarbazone, m. p. 218-19°) evidently identical with Banerjee's ketone (*loc. cit.*).

*Condensation of ω -Chloro-*p*-methoxypropioiophenone with Ethyl Sodio-acetoacetate: Formation of 3-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)- Δ^2 cyclohexenone (IX).*—Molecular sodium (1.72 g.) covered with benzene (20 c.c.) was cooled in ice and gradually mixed with ethyl acetoacetate (2.7 g.) and the product left overnight. A solution of ω -chloro-*p*-methoxypropioiophenone (Kenner and Statham, *loc. cit.*) (14.8 g.) was then added and the reaction allowed to proceed at the room temperature overnight. It was then heated on the steam-bath for 5-6 hours to complete the

reaction. On cooling the product was treated with ice and dilute hydrochloric acid. The benzene layer was removed, washed, dried, and the solvent evaporated. The residue (21 g.) consisting of a brown viscous oil could not be distilled without decomposition. The crude product (5 g.) was mixed with a solution of sodium hydroxide (2 g.) in water (200 c.c.) and the whole heated to boiling under reflux for 1 hour. It was cooled and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed, dried, and distilled. The residue on distillation under reduced pressure yielded a pale yellow oil (2 g.), b.p. $173^{\circ}/4\text{mm.}$ which rapidly solidified. On recrystallisation from petroleum ether (b.p. $60^{\circ}\text{-}80^{\circ}$) with the addition of a few drops of ethyl acetate it had m.p. 84° and consisted of 5-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)- Δ^2 -cyclohexenone. (Found: C, 76.8; H, 6.79. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 77.0; H, 6.9 per cent). There remained in the distillation flask a solid residue which was not further examined.

The semicarbazone, prepared in the usual way, crystallises from dilute alcohol, m.p. $218\text{-}19^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 64.2; H, 7.2. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3$ requires C, 65.0; H, 6.6 per cent).

The above unsaturated ketone on hydrogenation with Adam's platinum oxide catalyst rapidly absorbs one molecule of hydrogen giving 3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone (I), which was identified by the formation of the semicarbazone, m.p. and mixed m.p., $193\text{-}94^{\circ}$.

Further work is in progress.

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